

MAIN ISSUES OF PROFESSIONAL DIRECTION OF SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7860137>

Abstract. *In the article, the pedagogical and psychological significance of the measures taken in the direction of the cooperation of the family, neighborhood, and educational institutions in directing students to the profession, the orientation of general secondary school students to the profession, the choice of a profession, the development of the student as a qualified specialist in the future, the relevant social and opinions about the methods that create the basis for the formation of professional qualities are stated.*

Keywords: *career orientation, family, neighborhood, educational institutions, cooperation, pedagogy, psychology, career choice, student personality, expert, professional qualities.*

The strategic direction of the development of the education system in society is the intellectual and moral development of a person based on his purposeful independent activity in various fields. In the decision PQ-5140 of June 8, 2021, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of personnel training for working professions", vocational training of students of 10-11 grades of general secondary education institutions, based on the interests and abilities of students, in the future to create conditions for them to continue their education or engage in labor activities according to their occupations, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers was adopted and aimed at preparing the future generation as worthy personnel for the future of our country. Along with the developed countries of the world, the promotion of independent education is an important direction in the process of educational reforms. The research on the phenomenon of education of the professional competence of the pedagogue is expressed in the works of several scientists. These authors put forward the idea that together with the qualities of professional competence - reliability characterizes the teacher's pedagogical culture as a professional-individual phenomenon. In turn, the concept of professional competence, as stated by V.A. Slastenin, represents the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the pedagogue to carry out pedagogical activities and describes his professional formation.

The importance of choosing the right profession in the conditions of the market economy in the well-being of people, the demands of various professions; the world of professions, the family tree of professions, important professions in the national economy of Uzbekistan, classifier of professions; training system of junior specialists; occupations, working conditions, tools, science, purpose, students to learn about their interests and inclinations, the unique features of their character, their nervous structure, psyche, their abilities and needs a voluntary choice of schools for obtaining information about professions based on the requirements of the labor market of certain professions, changing needs, matching health with the chosen profession, education in secondary special, vocational educational institutions located in the region; it is necessary to know his future position from the possibilities of continuing his studies. Students can analyze professions; it is necessary to be able to correctly assess their personal qualities, interests, and

health levels, to be able to compare their characteristics with the demands of professions and to make personal professional plans.

Thanks to the reforms in the educational process, in a short period, Uzbekistan has achieved achievements recognized by the world's leading experts in the field of education. The main goal of educating the next generation is to prepare them to become professionals who can benefit society. After all, gaining one's place in society is achieved only by taking a certain profession.

Professional adaptation is the development of a person as a specialist, the formation of appropriate social and professional qualities in him, active creative work, the fulfillment of given instructions and requirements, and the creation of a system of activities that allows him to achieve high professional qualifications, choosing a suitable profession from among related professions. help is needed. People who help in choosing a suitable profession

- students;
- parents;
- educational institution;
- career guide;
- career guidance service specialists;
- teachers;
- class leader;
- school doctor;
- head of the library;
- public organizations;
- vocational education institutions;
- enterprises;
- labor bodies;
- regional management bodies (hokum);
- local self-government bodies;
- mass media.³

Today, the migration of able-bodied people, especially young people, their search for work abroad, and the influence of various criminal gangs, and in this regard, cooperation between parents, neighborhood activists, and educational institutions is extremely urgent. became an issue. Many parents, and pedagogues recognize the responsibility of parents, teachers, and neighborhood activists in guiding students to a profession, and in choosing a profession - the most important responsible person, i.e. they hardly comment on the student. However, choosing a profession is a matter that each young person must decide for himself. For this, older teachers, community members, and family members should create a foundation for teenagers and young adults not to make mistakes in choosing a profession.

During the 3rd year, I helped accept the documents of applicants at the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz, Nukus, Republic of Korokalpakstan. During this time, I was convinced that for some reason, some applicants do not know what profession they will take in the future. At the time of receiving the documents, you are interested in the applicants, Why do you want to transfer to this direction? I asked. I received the following answers from applicants.

Answers received from applicants	2016-2017- during the academic year	2017-2018- during the academic year	2018-2019- during the academic year
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I am very interested in this subject (prepared for tutoring)	30%	35%	40%
The number of applicants who submitted documents is small	40%	40%	40%
Last year's score was not high	20%	15%	10%
Because his friend or brother-in-law submitted documents	5%	5%	5%
Because of his parents	5%	5%	5%

In my opinion, it is necessary to analyze the above-mentioned "Differential Diagnostic Questionnaire" by experts and add appropriate changes and additions to it, on this basis it is necessary to come to a certain conclusion⁵. It is necessary to revive the work of conscious career choice of students and to increase the activity of parents and science teachers together with psychologists. In cooperation with existing academic lyceums and vocational colleges and higher education institutions, organizing events and meetings such as "Open Day", "Labor Fairs" and "Professions Festival" that help students to make informed career choices, involving leading experts in this process attraction is appropriate. It is desirable to acquire knowledge, skills, and qualifications in the world of professions from a young age, and to improve cooperation with parents for this purpose. Under the responsibility of school management and practicing psychologists, it is necessary to organize more individual and group consultations to achieve a conscious career choice among young students. It is necessary to revive the work carried out in the direction of the competence approach to education and to form practical skills and abilities within the framework of the subjects taught at school in the formation of the professional image of students. In conclusion, the formation of professional visions in a person can be determined based on professional interest and making a conscious decision about the future profession. Young people may make mistakes when choosing a profession due to their inability to adequately assess their capabilities and not consciously approach the choice. Inadequate information about professions among students, and lack of imagination in this regard cause difficulties in deciding on the choice of profession. In the educational system, the main goal should not only be to expand the scope of knowledge of students, but the first task should be to form skills and competencies necessary for life. Important steps have been taken in this regard. In particular, in the field of primary education, state educational standards based on the competence approach are being developed and implemented in the educational process. Based on this approach, the issue of forming the skills and competencies that are necessary for students in real-life situations is set as a priority. In the process of guiding students to a profession, the family, neighborhood, and educational institutions, which are the institutions of socialization of a person in society, and the persons directly responsible for this process, parents, teachers, the vocational guidance class leaders, psychologist, dermatologist, doctor, children's leader, club leaders, library staff, neighborhood activists, neighbors, relatives, peers, regional labor market officials, mass media,

cooperation of close enterprises organization is important. First of all, it is necessary to take into account the student's professional need, motivation, ability, interest, and ability. Otherwise, a general referral or instruction will not lead to a positive result, because individuality requires specific requirements. Vocational knowledge should consist of an impressive set of information aimed at introducing students to the nature of the profession and its requirements for the individual. Organizing the participation and cooperation of all sections of society in conveying this information to the minds of young people is the most urgent task of today.

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